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“PATIENCE WITH PRAYER”

Through hands raised high, my heart stays quiet,
Trusting God's time, obeying His will.
No hurry, no fear, just happy charm,
Every test has its place.

I pray with hope, though trials come,
I kneel in prayer, with lifted eyes.
The waiting aches, the days feel long,
But faith, not gossip, keeps me strong.

Like seed once buried, dark and deep,
Will grow with time no need to weep.
For patience mixed with prayers so true,
Will bring blessed fruit in the season due.

So I will wait, not lose my way,
For blessings come to those who stay.
With steadfast trust, my soul will see,
That all God's plans will provide for me.